

This paper is published at Journal of World Neurosurg.

DOI: 10.1016/j.wneu.2023.12.058

Rostami, A., Elyassirad, D., Vatanparast, M., Abouei Mehrizi, M. A., [Hasanpour, M.](#), Rezaee, H., Haghiri, A., Keykhosravi, E. (2024)

Functional Outcome and Mortality Predictors in Patients with Cerebral Ischemic Infarction After Decompressive Craniectomy: Cross-Sectional Study

Abstract:

OBJECTIVE: Surgeons commonly perform Decompressive craniectomy (DC) to manage patients with cerebral ischemic infarction. However, there are conflicting data on the long-term functional outcomes following DC. Therefore, this study aims to determine the functional outcome of patients with cerebral ischemic infarction after DC. **METHODS:** This prospective and retrospective cross-sectional study included 148 patients with cerebral ischemic infarction who underwent DC at Ghaem Hospital, Mashhad, Iran, from March 2011 to March 2021. The Modified Rankin Scale (mRS) assesses disability in these patients and determines the recovery and degree of long-term functional outcomes. Demographic and clinical data were extracted and recorded in a researcher-made questionnaire. **RESULTS:** In summary, the follow-up revealed a survival rate of 39.2% among patients with ischemic stroke. The comparison of the mean infarct volume in patients with various mRS scores showed that the mean infarct volume was significantly higher in patients with unfavorable functional outcomes, based on mRS scores at discharge ($P = 0.05$), 3 months mRS ($P < 0.01$), and mRS score at final follow-up ($P = 0.01$). Final mortality was higher in patients with higher mRS scores at discharge, after 3 months, and final follow-up ($P < 0.01$). Older age and infarction volume can predict mRS and mortality in patients with ischemic stroke ($P < 0.01$). **CONCLUSIONS:** The present study showed that mortality and mRS scores at various times are associated with infarction volume and older age in patients with ischemic stroke.

Keywords: Decompressive craniectomy, Functional outcome, Infarction volume, Ischemic stroke

[Mohammad Hasanpour](#) Contact Info:

✉ Dr.m.hpr@gmail.com

[Mohammad Hasanpour](#) Available at :

Google scholar: <https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=IPyeGnYAAAAJ&hl=en>

Scopus: <https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=55696962500>

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4109-0893>

ResearchGate: <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Mohammad-Hasanpour-9>

Web of Science: <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/author/record/LVR-6050-2024>

SSRN: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/cf_dev/AbsByAuth.cfm?per_id=7241783

ZENODO: <https://zenodo.org/me/uploads?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Bepress: <https://works.bepress.com/mohammad-hasanpour/>

Figshare: https://figshare.com/authors/Mohammad_Hasanpour/20360460